

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND ENERGY ABSORPTION OF LAMINATES WITH DIFFERENT POROSITY CONTENTS

Helmuth Toftegaard and Svend Ib Andersen
Materials Department
Risø National Laboratory, Roskilde, Denmark

ABSTRACT

The mechanical properties of a quasi-isotropic polymer composite with three different levels of porosity were obtained from static materials tests. The energy absorption during the static tests is compared to the energy absorption under low velocity impact. The composite consists of plain glass weave in a PET matrix, and the porosity levels are 2-3, 11-12 and 16-17 % by volume. The density of absorbed energy found for in-plane tension, out-of-plane shear and impact all have a maximum at 11-12 vol-% porosity. The results indicate the existence of an optimum porosity level with respect to energy density for this material.

INTRODUCTION

Polymer reinforced composite materials are used in a number of general engineering applications, where among other things the energy absorption capability of the material or component is of importance. This is the case for structures which can be exposed to collision loads such as vehicles and ships, for protective shielding against debris from accidents and especially for light weight armour materials, where glass-reinforced polymers are used separately or in combination with ceramic tiles.

The impact behaviour of composite laminates can often be described with sufficient accuracy by the static behaviour, at least for design purposes. This is shown to be valid even for ballistic impact, and the static punch-through curve is used in [1] for prediction of residual velocities and ballistic limits. Further references for both high and low velocity impact are given in [1], and in the following it is assumed, that the static material characteristics at least qualitatively describe the materials dynamic behaviour as experienced during impact conditions.

The present study of the relationship between porosity content and energy absorption capability has been performed as part of a project on light weight armour, where one of the material parameters has been the porosity content. Extensive static materials testing has been used for initial characterisation of the materials in order to establish data for modelling purposes. In addition, low velocity impact tests have been performed on full thickness specimens, and the results regarding energy absorption have been compared for the two cases.

MATERIALS

The composite is a laminate of E-glass fibres in a nearly balanced plain weave with an area density of 810 g/m² and PET (polyethylene terephthalate) thermo-plastic matrix. Laminates with quasi-isotropic lay-up were manufactured to 3 porosity levels - low (2-3 vol-%), medium (11-12 vol-%) and high (16-17 vol-%). The laminates were made in two thicknesses (4 and 24 mm). [0#90 / 45#-45 / 90#0 / -45#45]_s and [0#90 / 45#-45 / 90#0 / -45#45]_{es} is the stacking sequence for the 4 and 24 mm laminate, respectively. The notation A#B is used for a weave with warp direction A and weft direction B.

The laminate lay-up was made by a film-stacking technique with alternating layers of glass fibre weave and PET film. The laminates were consolidated in an autoclave. The different porosity levels and thicknesses were obtained by varying the fibre/matrix ratio and the autoclave pressure and vacuum.

EXPERIMENTS

In-plane tensile tests were performed on 4 mm laminates, while out-of-plane shear tests and low velocity impact tests were performed on 24 mm laminates. In-plane and out-of-plane refer to the plane of the laminate.

Figure 1. Flat waisted tensile sample with dimensions in mm. Thickness 4 mm.

Figure 2. Double notch shear sample with dimensions in mm.

TENSION TESTS

The in-plane tension tests were performed on flat waisted specimens (Fig. 1). The specimens were cut with an abrasive water jet. They were equipped with endtabs and strain gauge couples 0°/90° on both sides. Preliminary tests with the chosen specimen size and a larger size were performed to investigate any possible influence from the weave structure on the strength. The chosen size specimens gave the same results as the larger specimens. All tensile tests were performed on a standard hydraulic testing machine with a displacement velocity of 0.5 mm/min. The tests were terminated when the load was clearly decreasing.

SHEAR TESTS

The out-of-plane shear tests were performed on double notched beams (Fig. 2) with the length and height direction in the 0° direction and thickness direction of the laminate, respectively. They were cut with a diamond coated cutting wheel and equipped with strain gauge couples +45°/-45° on both sides. A special test fixture was used (Fig. 3) to load the specimens in a standard hydraulic testing machine with a displacement velocity of 0.3 mm/min. The maximum strain that could be measured by each strain gauge was limited to 4 % by the data acquisition set-up. This

set-up was not optimized to measure strain energy alone but also shear modulus and was thus a compromise between high maximum strain and reasonable resolution. The tests were terminated when the specimens obtained hard contact with the part of the test fixture near the alignment pin (see Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Shear test fixture (modified Wyoming fixture).

Figure 4. Impact sample with strain gauge locations on front (G2) and back (G1 and G3).

IMPACT TESTS

Low velocity impact testing was performed on 24 mm thick rectangular panels 200x175 mm clamped between 38 mm thick steel flanges with eight 12 mm bolts placed at a radius of 88 mm. The steel flanges had a circular window, radius 68 mm, and the impact tested specimen can somewhat simplified be considered to be a circular disc clamped at a radius of 68 mm (Fig. 4).

The whole assembly was bolted to the floor supports under the drop-weight testing machine at Aalborg University. This equipment is designed for relatively high impact energies as required for these panel dimensions. The drop weight tower is 6 m high and equipped with two falling weights with masses 10.4 and 30.3 kg. The usable height of the tower is lower for the larger mass, as the cross-section of the mass is constant and then the length larger, leading to a slightly lower impact velocity for the larger mass. The masses were mounted with a spherical impactor head with radius 25 mm. The velocity of the impactor was measured immediately before and after impact. During impact, the strain was measured at three different locations, two at the backside of the plate and one at the impact side (Fig. 4).

For the material in question, 2 specimens were tested for each porosity content but for two different impact energies: 500 and 900 J. The data from the velocity measuring device and the strain signals were stored on tape recorder for later treatment.

RESULTS

The materials tests are used to obtain stiffness, strength and strain energy density in tension and shear. From the impact tests the absorbed energy can be measured. The ultra-sonic profile measurements together with thickness measurements lead to estimates of the volume damaged by impact, and thus to estimates of absorbed energy density.

TENSION TESTS

The longitudinal strains measured on both sides of the specimen are averaged to obtain a resulting longitudinal strain, ϵ_{long} . The transverse strain is evaluated in a similar manner. In this way the tension strains can be separated from the bending strains. The stress, σ , is load divided by average width and average thickness over the gauge length of the specimen.

For some tests the longitudinal strain measurement failed before the maximum load was reached. In those cases a constant strain rate is assumed after measurement failure. The assumed strain rate is adjusted to obtain a smooth transition from measured to estimated strain. Examples of the resulting stress-strain curves are shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Examples of in-plane tension stress-strain curves for 3 different porosities.

Figure 6. Examples of out-of-plane shear stress-strain curves for 3 different porosities.

The obtained Young's modulus, E , Poisson's ratio, ν , the largest measured stress, σ_{peak} , associated strain, ϵ_{peak} , and associated strain energy density, u_{peak} , are given in Table 1 together with the relative standard deviation (std). E and ν are evaluated between 0 and 0.1 % strain; and u_{peak} is the area below the σ - ϵ_{long} curve up to ϵ_{peak} . The values of u_{peak} for the different porosity levels are shown in Fig. 10.

Table 1. In-plane tension results.

Porosity [vol-%]	E [GPa]	std [%]	ν	std [%]	ϵ_{peak} [%]	std [%]	σ_{peak} [MPa]	std [%]	u_{peak} [MJ/m ³]	std [%]
3	30	2	0.27	6	1.5	15	230	2	2.0	21
12	22	7	0.23	9	2.1	10	190	0.4	2.5	13
16	20	12	0.26	10	1.5	13	140	6	1.3	21

SHEAR TESTS

The shear strain, γ , is taken as the average of the engineering shear strains on front and back side of the specimen: $\gamma = (\gamma_{\text{front}} + \gamma_{\text{back}})/2$ with $\gamma_{\text{front}} = (\epsilon_{+45} - \epsilon_{-45})_{\text{front}}$ and $\gamma_{\text{back}} = (\epsilon_{+45} - \epsilon_{-45})_{\text{back}}$. In this way the shear strains can be separated from the twisting strains. The maximum value of $|\gamma_{\text{front}}|$ and $|\gamma_{\text{back}}|$ that can be measured (due to the set-up of the data acquisition system) is 8 % - for $\epsilon_{+45} = -4\%$ and $\epsilon_{-45} = +4\%$. The shear stress, τ , is load divided by the average height and average width of the cross-section between the notches of the specimen. No factors have been used to correct for inhomogeneous stress and strain fields in the volume of the specimen between the notches.

For some tests the shear strain measurement failed, or the maximum of 8 % shear strain was reached before the maximum load. In those cases a constant strain rate is assumed after measurement failure or after the 8 % strain was reached. The assumed strain rate is adjusted to obtain a smooth transition from measured to estimated strain. Examples of the resulting stress-strain curves are shown in Fig. 6.

The obtained shear modulus, G , the largest measured stress, τ_{peak} , associated strain, γ_{peak} , and associated strain energy density, u_{peak} , are given in Table 2 together with the relative standard deviation (std). G is evaluated between 0 and 0.1 % strain; and u_{peak} is the area below the τ - γ curve up to γ_{peak} . The values of u_{peak} for the different porosity levels are shown in Fig. 10.

Table 2. Out-of-plane shear test results.

Porosity [vol-%]	G [GPa]	std [%]	γ_{peak} [%]	std [%]	τ_{peak} [MPa]	std [%]	u_{peak} [MJ/m ³]	std [%]
2	6.6	12	2.2	17	42	3	0.4	19
11	1.4	5	14	7	18	5	1.1	11
17	0.73	4	14	7	11	1	0.6	8

IMPACT TESTS

The strain-time history for gauges placed at R=35 mm are shown in Fig. 7 for a plate with 12 % porosity content. Initially, the plate deforms in bending as indicated by the opposite signs of the strain with compressive strains at the backside, but later in the impact event the in-plane stretching is larger than bending, leading to tensile strains at both sides of the panel and ending with permanent tensile strains after the event. This behaviour is observed for all specimens and indicates, that both in-plane and out-of-plane properties are relevant for this type of loading.

The maximum measured strain rates experienced during testing are in the range 65 - 165 s⁻¹ in the central part of the plates as measured on the backside, and with the highest rates for the low porosity material. The strain rates are reduced with the distance from the centre of the plate, and for the gauges placed at R=35 mm the maximum rates measured are in the range 25 - 45 s⁻¹.

After testing, the shape of the impacted surface was measured by ultrasonic c-scan technique for all 6 specimens, and an example of the results is shown as a time-of-flight plot in Fig. 8. The figure shows the "negative" image of the surface - the central peak representing the indentation of the impact side of the plate. The deformations of this side are seen to be localized around the position of impact. From the plots the influenced or damaged surface area as well as the

maximum permanent indentation is evaluated. The extent of the damaged surface in two perpendicular directions are averaged and used as an equivalent circle diameter to estimate the damaged area. The permanent deformations of the backside were smaller and more evenly distributed over the surface. Due to practical problems the backside of the specimens was not measured with the ultrasonic c-scan technique. As the shape is very smooth, it is difficult to determine an area directly from the surface shape as for the impact side. Assuming the impact side is nearly unaffected at a distance from the impact location, the deviation of plate thickness from the original thickness may be taken as an indication of permanent backside deformations. From the sectioned plates, the radius for a thickness increase of 0.2 mm was measured, and an influenced area on the backside can thus be defined.

Figure 7. Example of strains measured from the strain gauge at R=35 mm on front and back of specimen, respectively.

Figure 8. Ultra-sonic c-scan plot showing the "negative image of an impacted surface - the central peak represents the indentation.

For the specimens exposed to 900 Joule incoming energy the whole backside area within the window (R=68 mm) was deformed, and the results indicate that a larger specimen would be able to absorb more energy. This is also true to some extent for the 17 % porosity plate at the 500 J level.

The measured impactor velocities before and after impact and the corresponding energies are shown in Table 3 for all tests.

Table 3. Impact results.

Mass [kg]	Porosity [vol-%]	Velocity [m/s]		Energy [J]	
		before impact	after impact	before impact	after impact
10.4	2	9.9	6.5	507	220
	11	9.9	6.3	507	206
	17	9.8	5.2	494	141
30.3	2	8.0	4.9	946	364
	11	7.9	4.4	970	293
	17	8.0	3.9	970	230

The difference in kinetic energy of the impactor before and after impact is absorbed by the test set-up. If we ignore the energy transmitted and absorbed by the specimen support plate, the energy dissipated by the specimens are equal to the difference between the two energies in Table 3. The energy dissipated by the specimens is shown in Fig. 9 as function of the porosity content and normalised with the incoming energy and the results for the low porosity material. The specimens with the highest porosity content have absorbed most energy.

Figure 9. Normalized absorbed energy in low velocity impact tests with low energy (500 J) and high energy (900 J).

Figure 10. Peak energy density for in-plane tension, out-of-plane shear and low energy impact load.

Finally, a "damage"-volume is defined as the volume delimited by two concentric circular areas (each with an area equivalent to the respective damage areas at the impact side and backside) and by the cone connecting these two. This "damage"-volume can be used to obtain the energy density for the low energy impact tests as function of porosity. The results are shown in Fig. 10 together with the peak energy density obtained from the materials testing.

DISCUSSION

The mechanical properties change with increasing porosity content: the stiffness and maximum stress decreases, while the strain at maximum stress is largest at the medium porosity level (the shear strain at maximum stress is 14 % for both medium and high porosity). The strain energy density for both the tension and the shear tests is largest for the medium porosity.

The strains are estimated in the cases where the tension or shear strain measurements fail, or where the shear strains exceed 8 %. The shear strains for the low porosity are well below 8 %, but those for the medium and high porosity extend to an estimated value of 14%. However the strain-time curves for these tests show a constant strain rate from 5 to 8 %. This makes the assumption of constant strain rate from 8 to 14 % reasonable.

The average shear stress was used instead of the local stress corresponding to the measured local shear strain. The stress factor ($SF = \tau_{local}/\tau_{average}$) depends mainly on the specimen geometry and the E modulus ratio ($ER = E_L/E_H$) of E_L in the length direction (in-plane) and E_H in the height direction (out-of-plane) of the shear specimen. The geometry is the same for all specimens, but ER is expected to increase since the out-of-plane stiffness is expected to decrease more than the in-plane stiffness with increasing porosity. According to [2] the relative change in SF for the same geometry is in the order of 20 % for a change in ER from 5 to 15. A change of 20 % in SF will not shift the maximum u_{peak} away from the medium porosity, since u_{peak} at the medium

porosity is so much larger (1.8 - 2.8 times) than u_{peak} at low and high porosity.

Both the tension and shear tests were terminated while the specimens were still able to carry load, and the reported strain energy density is thus based only on the first part of the total stress-strain curve.

The sectioned impact specimens showed delaminations and indentation (crushing) as the major damage types for the low porosity materials. For the plates with the moderate and high void content the produced damage was much more difficult to envisage. For all plates the thickness (and thus the volume) was increased due to impact.

For the low energy impact the energy densities from the impact tests correlate well with peak energy densities measured during materials testing, indicating that there is an optimum as function of porosity content. For the high energy impact the volume able to dissipate energy seems to be restricted by the applied impact specimen size, and larger specimens should be used in order to estimate the impact damaged volume (and absorbed energy density).

CONCLUSION

The material properties for in-plane tension and out-of-plane shear together with the impact response have been investigated for 3 different porosity levels. The stiffness and maximum stress decreases with increasing porosity, while the strain at maximum stress is largest at the medium porosity level.

The largest strain energy density in tension and in shear together with the largest absorbed impact energy density is found at the medium porosity level.

The combined interpretation of results from impact testing and from static materials testing indicates the existence of an optimum porosity level for this material when applied as an energy absorber.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The work was financed partly by the EUCLID RTP 3.2 project. The cooperation and work of DEMEX Consulting Engineers A/S and Aalborg University is highly appreciated. The authors thank the following staff members at the Materials Department at Risø for contributing to the work: Mr. Jan Larsen, mr. Frank Adrian and Dr. Ole Jørgensen.

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